

UZBEKISTAN IS AT THE PRESENT STAGE OF CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT

D.B.Rustamova, M.T.Egamova, G.R.Marupova, B.P.Matyokubov

*Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University named after Mirzo
Ulugbek*

Abstract: *At the present stage of development of construction, when high-inertia enclosing structures are replaced by low-inertia - lightweight ones, regulation of the microclimate of buildings using external enclosing structures is becoming one of the important methods. For our climate, the problem of protecting buildings from overheating due to strong solar radiation in summer is one of the most pressing. This article examines the reasons for overheating of buildings in summer, mainly due to excess heat entering through external building envelopes - walls, windows and cladding.*

Keywords: *outdoor air, average temperature, thermal insulation, microclimate, coatings, thermal-physical, temperature, construction.*

The amount of heat introduced through vertical structures depends on their orientation to the cardinal points, on their heat-shielding qualities and the type of finish of the outer surface layer. The amount of heat introduced through the coating is determined by its design. More heat enters the room through attic coverings than through attic coverings. The problem of reducing heat flow into the room through external enclosing structures in the summer, especially horizontal ones, is one of the main ones when designing these structures. Practice shows that with sufficiently constant average temperatures of the outside air and exposure to solar radiation for a sufficiently long period of time, in the absence of operational heat emissions, air exchange and heat captured by windows, an average temperature is established in the room equal to the average total temperature of the outside air, regardless of the type and thermal insulation capacity of external enclosing structures. But this does not mean that the indoor microclimate can be changed only by using artificial cooling means. One should strive to make maximum use of architectural and structural measures to reduce heat gain through building envelopes in the summer, especially since cold is 3 times more expensive than heat. To reduce overheating of the surfaces of vertical enclosing structures, for example, windows, the use of sun protection devices is proposed as an architectural and structural measure. Attic combined (usually flat, horizontal) roofs are that part of the building through which a significant amount of heat can enter the room in the summer, since these structures are exposed to solar radiation more intensely and for a longer time compared to vertical structures.

Any building is topped with an attic or non-attic covering. This part of the building is subject to a complex set of external force and non-force influences. The quality of the microclimate created in the premises largely depends on their performance. Research conducted in Tashkent has shown that with insufficient

thermal protection of buildings in the summer, the average daily temperature in the premises reaches 30 °C or more, and in some hours up to 35 °C. At the same time, the temperature in the premises of the top floors of multi-storey buildings is 3-4 °C higher than on the middle floors. These temperature conditions far exceed the comfortable level regulated by the relevant hygienic regulations. In Uzbekistan, the optimal temperature in residential premises during the warm season is considered to be 26-27 °C.

Attic coverings of residential buildings, as a rule, are designed according to the following scheme: load-bearing slab, vapor barrier, thermal insulation, leveling layer of cement-sand mortar, waterproofing carpet and protective layer of white gravel. With such a design scheme, the sufficient thermal resistance of the structure for winter conditions is usually clearly insufficient to ensure thermal stability in summer conditions. Therefore, the thickness of the insulating layer is often increased compared to what is required for winter conditions.

Structural diagram of a continuous roofless roof of a building

The aesthetic requirements of people must be satisfied with high quality and artistic design of the interior spaces of homes, facade decoration, architecture of buildings and surrounding buildings.

It is practically impossible to answer the question of where it is better, more pleasant and more convenient for people to live - in their own low-rise building or in an ordinary apartment. Some people prefer a small or even small apartment in an ordinary apartment building with all the amenities; they believe that there will be less hassle, someone will always take care of heating the apartment, cleaning the yard, and so on.

Others also believe that there is nothing nicer and better than your own personal home, even in the suburbs or in nature. Even if not with all the normal amenities, but with your own plot of land.

Today, all over the world, under the influence of scientific and technological progress society, changes have occurred in building materials and structures, construction technologies, engineering equipment and operating systems for low-rise housing.

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